

HAMK CoARA project: Strengthening the Qualitative Criteria for the Researcher Assessment

 Pakolliset kysymykset merkitty tähdellä (*)

Consent to participate in the study SuHAMK CoARAb Survey, Spring 2025
"Strengthening the Qualitative Criteria for the Researcher Assessment at Häme University of Applied Sciences."

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The objective of the SuHAMK CoARAb project is to strengthen the researcher evaluation criteria at Häme University of Applied Sciences (HAMK) to better incorporate qualitative metrics into the researcher assessment process. The project will define these criteria through collaboration with various stakeholders, including researchers at different career stages, supervisors, and the researcher evaluation group at HAMK. The survey is part of the above-mentioned collaboration.

Before continuing with this survey kindly familiarize yourself with the SuHAMK CoARAb **data protection notice** (can be found as an attachment in the original email).

By continuing with this survey, you agree to the following:

- I agree to participate in the SuHAMK CoARAb project survey mentioned above, which aims to develop qualitative researcher evaluation criteria at Häme University of Applied Sciences.
- I agree to the processing of my personal data as mentioned in **data protection notice** (can be found as an attachment in the original email).
- I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I can withdraw my consent at any time without giving any reason.
- I am aware that if I stop the study or if I withdraw my consent, the information collected about me until then will be destroyed.

Introducing the SuHAMK CoARAb Project!

What is the SuHAMK CoARAb Project?

The objective of this project is to strengthen the researcher evaluation criteria and the researcher evaluation process at HAMK. This includes identifying and developing qualitative evaluation metrics which are better able to recognize diverse researcher skills and support different

researcher career paths.

Why is the SuHAMK CoARAb Project Important?

The SuHAMK CoARA project is part of the CoARA Boost project. CoARA Boost is a Horizon Europe-funded project designed to bring research assessment beyond its current simplistic reliance on journal-based quantitative indicators and quantity over quality metrics.

CoARA is on a mission to improve researcher assessments and create international evaluation frameworks which are capable of emphasizing research quality, transparency, and actively involve diverse stakeholders in the evaluation process.

How Can You Contribute?

The main stakeholders of the HAMK evaluation process are HAMK researchers, researcher supervisors and the researcher evaluation team. We want to collect YOUR opinions, perspectives and feedback!

This survey aims to collect a background understanding of the opinions, perspectives and wishes of HAMK researchers, researcher supervisors and the researcher evaluation team.

1. Research unit *

- HAMK Bio
- HAMK Edu
- HAMK Tech

2. Year of experience in research

- 0–5
- 6–10
- 11 or more

3. Years active at HAMK (since recruitment as researcher)

- 0–5
- 6–10

11 or more

4. Were you recruited to HAMK: *

Internally

Externally

5. When recruited to HAMK did you complete the tenure track? *

Yes

No

6. To what extent do you agree with the following? *

Completely disagree Somewhat disagree Somewhat agree Completely agree

The researcher assessment should consider the **impact of produced research?**

7. Please explain your answer.

8. To what extent do you agree with the following? *

Completely disagree Somewhat disagree Somewhat agree Completely agree

The researcher assessment should consider the **influence of the researcher?**

9. Please explain your answer.

10. To what extent do you think that the influence of researchers at UAS's can be demonstrated by the following? *

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Role in funding applications	<input type="radio"/>				
Role in published publications or other products or formats of research (suc as patents, technology, software, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaboration with different academic fields in projects or research related activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaboration with different stakeholders in projects or research related activities (such as businesses, policymakers, non-profit organizations etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaboration with a diverse range of people from different backgrounds	<input type="radio"/>				
Collaboration with UAS study units	<input type="radio"/>				
Participation in local research conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.	<input type="radio"/>				
Participation in international conferences, lectures, webinars, presentations, panels etc.	<input type="radio"/>				
Participation in research mobility programs	<input type="radio"/>				
Role in teaching activities	<input type="radio"/>				

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Feedback on teaching activities from students and/or colleagues	<input type="radio"/>				
Role in researcher supervision activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Feedback on supervision activities from students and/or colleagues	<input type="radio"/>				
Range of different methodological skills utilized in projects, research activities, teaching activities and supervision activities	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of different formats of communication (such as articles, presentations, speeches, workshops etc)	<input type="radio"/>				
Experience in communicating with different audiences (such as academic audiences, policymakers, private businesses, ordinary citizens etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

11. To what extent do you think that the impact of research at UAS's can be demonstrated by the following? *

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Multiple authors or research contributors	<input type="radio"/>				
Use of a multidisciplinary approach (such as authors from different academic fields, inclusion of multiple academic fields in publications, presentation of research at multidisciplinary conferences etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Research conducted in collaboration with stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				
Research conducted in collaboration with diverse stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>				

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Demonstrated relevance of research to current local societal issues	<input type="radio"/>				
Demonstrated relevance of research to current international societal issues	<input type="radio"/>				
Demonstrated relevance of research in future (expected duration of research relevance)	<input type="radio"/>				
Demonstrated practical applicability of research in local society (applicable to local businesses, local non-profit organizations, local non-profit institutions, local policies etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Demonstrated practical applicability of research in international society (applicable to international businesses, international non-profit organizations, international government institutions etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Demonstrated practical applicability of research in UAS study units	<input type="radio"/>				
Accessibility of research at all levels of society (such as academics, private business owners, policymakers, educators, ordinary citizens etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				

12. To what extent can the following be used demonstrate researcher skills in cooperation and collaboration? *

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Participation in either funding applications or research, which has multidisciplinary involvement?	<input type="radio"/>				

	Completely disagree	Somewhat disagree	Unsure	Somewhat agree	Completely agree
Participation in either funding applications or research, which considers multistakeholder involvement?	<input type="radio"/>				
Researcher involvement with other academic institutions?	<input type="radio"/>				
Researcher involvement with private sector institutions?	<input type="radio"/>				
Researcher involvement in UAS study units?	<input type="radio"/>				
Researcher involvement with other societal institutions?	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Anything else? Please specify.

How can researchers demonstrate having the following skills?

14. Effective communication skills? *

15. Ability to market ideas, research and projects? *

16. Ability to learn and cooperate? *

17. Ability to be flexible with ideas and respond to new research and findings? *

18. Ability to write cohesive strategies and plans? *

19. In your opinion, what do you think are the biggest challenges early career researchers face during the researcher assessment?

20. In your opinion, what do you think are the biggest challenges for researchers from diverse backgrounds during the researcher assessment?

21. In your opinion, which criteria is the most effective for evaluating the capabilities of a researcher? *

22. Any additional comments or feedback regarding the assessment criteria for researchers?
